

THE USE OF GINGER FOR MEDICINAL DISEASES BASED ON TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521581>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 07-January 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 10- January 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 17- January 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

ginger, antiallergic, antioxidant, Vitamin, Ayurveda, Mineral, dysmenorrheal, Drug.

ABSTRACT

The history of the use of ginger in cooking and pharmacology goes back about 5,000 years. It has long been valued for its taste and medicinal qualities, used for digestive problems, colds, fatigue and muscle pain, and was also considered a powerful aphrodisiac. Very popular in Europe in the 18th century and later, it was immortalized by famous artists including Van Gogh, Cezanne and Toussaint. Let's learn more about the benefits of ginger and precautions when using it from a scientific point of view.

Ginger is mentioned in ancient Chinese, Indian and Persian medical treatises as a tonic, antipyretic and cleansing agent. In Malaysia and India it is a well-known medicinal plant, especially in the ancient Indian medicine Ayurveda. Today it is used throughout the world to treat intestinal diseases, influenza-like infections and to restore shape after illness.

Ginger is rich in vitamins and minerals, contains essential oil, starch and the substance oleoresin, consisting of shogaol and gingerol - compounds with anti-inflammatory and antiemetic effects that accelerate intestinal transit. Fresh rhizomes contain a lot of copper, which is a cofactor for some enzymes in metabolic processes and is also involved in the formation of hemoglobin and collagen.

Ginger (*zingiber officinale*) is a plant of the Ginger family (Zingiberaceae), growing in most tropical and sunny regions of the planet, especially in Asia (India, China, Nepal). It belongs to the same family as turmeric and is considered a superfood today. Its aerial part consists of lanceolate leaves, a stem about a meter high, similar in appearance to reeds, yellow flowers with a red lip and fruits with a few black seeds. The main value of the plant lies in the underground branched part called the root or rhizome. Its yellow flesh serves as a reserve for the plant and ensures its survival.

Ginger is believed to have first appeared in southern India and China, but its wild ancestors have never been discovered. It was one of the first oriental spices to enter Europe: it has been known in France since the 9th century, and in England since the 10th century. During the conquest, the Spanish introduced it to the West Indies and Mexico, so that from the mid-16th century, Spain was able to import the precious spice from this part of the globe.

Since ancient times, the root has been used in food as a seasoning to garnish dishes, and also for its reputation as an aphrodisiac for men. Modern science debunks this quality of the plant. However, although ginger does not increase libido, it does have energizing properties and can stimulate sexuality.

Ginger is mentioned in ancient Chinese, Indian and Persian medical treatises as a tonic, antipyretic and cleansing agent. In Malaysia and India it is a well-known medicinal plant, especially in the ancient Indian medicine Ayurveda. Today it is used throughout the world to treat intestinal diseases, influenza-like infections and to restore shape after illness.

Vitamins and microelements (daily value): • Vitamin C - 5 mg (5.6%) Vitamin E - 0.3 mg (1.7%) Vitamin K - 0.1 mg (0.1%) Vitamin B3 - 0.7 mg (33%) Vitamin B6 - 0.2 mg (8%) Folic acid - 11 mcg (3.8%) Vitamin B5 - 0.2 mg (4.1%) Minerals in ginger Calcium - 16 mg (1.6%) Iron - 0.6 mg (3%) Magnesium - 43 mg (11%) Phosphorus - 34 mg (4%) Potassium - 415 mg (16%) Sodium - 13 mg (1%) Zinc - 0.34 mg (3%) Copper - 0.226 mg (22.6%) Magnesium - 0.43 mg (21%) Selenium - 0.7 µg (1%) Manganese - 0.229 mg (11%).

This composition determines the healing properties of ginger: Stimulates appetite and eliminates eating disorders (nausea, vomiting, bloating, gas, intestinal pain) Fights infections and colds (flu, cough, sore throat, fever, fatigue, loss of strength, muscle pain and joints, injuries) Relieves pain (migraines, menstruation, digestive cramps, stomach disorders) Prevents vomiting due to motion sickness, during pregnancy, post-operative or in connection with chemotherapy Prevents certain types of cancer (colon, intestinal, ovarian) Helps with heart disease vascular diseases Applied externally, relieves rheumatic, muscle and joint pain in arthritis, sprains, fractures, tendinitis, sciatica. Tones, stimulates and strengthens the body, protects the body's cells from aging. Well-known antioxidant

Ginger contains at least 40 antioxidant compounds. After thirty tests, along with turmeric, mint, coriander, broccoli and Brussels sprouts, it was included as one of the fourteen fresh vegetables with the strongest antioxidants.

The fresh root has stronger antioxidant activity compared to other vegetables and spices consumed in Asia. The main active compounds responsible for the pungent taste of fresh ginger are gingerols. Their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties are well known, and their anticancer potential has been demonstrated in vitro. A recent study has shown the promising effects of ginger as a therapeutic agent in the treatment of prostate cancer.

When ginger is dried, gingerols are converted into compounds called shogaols. Research shows they may protect cells from Alzheimer's disease.

The effects of various antioxidant compounds isolated from ginger have been observed in vitro as well as in animals. A particularly powerful antioxidant effect was obtained when ginger was consumed in combination with garlic or onions. The synergy between different antioxidant compounds allows them to surpass their individual effects on the body.

The anti-inflammatory properties of some components of ginger have long been known and are well documented in vitro. They are most pronounced in gingerol, a phenolic compound

that gives the root its pungent taste. Shogaols and paradols also exhibit anti-inflammatory effects through various mechanisms. In humans, ginger consumption has shown promising results in reducing pain associated with arthritis in relation to muscle pain and primary dysmenorrhea. The detrimental effect of ginger on the herpes virus, respiratory syncytial virus, and in particular the influenza virus was also determined.

Research on the antibacterial and antifungal properties of ginger has shown its effectiveness against bacteria: *Helicobacter pylori*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Streptococcus mutans*, as well as strains of fungi *Candida albicans* and *Candida krusei*. On the other hand, the results of these studies are difficult to compare, given the different preparations and the amount of ginger used (from 0.5 g to 50 g per day). Therefore, more research is needed before concluding the real impact of fresh ginger consumption on the prevention and treatment of pain associated with chronic inflammatory diseases.

May Improve Blood Sugar Levels A recent rigorous scientific study has demonstrated the beneficial effects of consuming 3 grams of ginger powder for 8 weeks in people with type 2 diabetes. Indeed, ginger extract reduces fasting blood sugar and glycated hemoglobin levels in addition to improving insulin resistance.

Affects blood pressure The property of ginger to lower blood pressure has been used in folk medicine for many years. It eliminates spasm of peripheral vessels, thins the blood, saturates it with oxygen and has a warming effect, helping to lower blood pressure. Regular consumption of the root helps cleanse blood vessels of bad cholesterol, prevents the formation of blood clots and improves the functioning of the cardiovascular system.

An Effective Anti-Nausea Remedy Known as a natural and powerful anti-nausea remedy, ginger is highly valued by pregnant women, especially during the first trimester. To date, most randomized studies have been conducted with ginger powder and comparing it with placebo. Two studies have shown that taking 0.5 to 1.5 grams of powdered ginger (in capsule form) may be effective in treating nausea and vomiting during pregnancy. Indeed, the active ingredients contained in ginger rhizome have a soothing effect on the gastric mucosa and relieve symptoms of gastritis, gastrointestinal disorders such as nausea, vomiting, bloating and abdominal pain.

Additionally, a recent meta-analysis shows that 1 g of powdered ginger (in capsule form) is more effective than placebo in preventing nausea and vomiting after surgery. For comparison, 1 to 2 grams of ground ginger is equivalent to about 10 grams of fresh ginger. However, some studies have found no antiemetic effect after consuming fresh ginger. In any case, gingerols and shogaols contained in ginger play a role in the antiemetic effect by acting to reduce stomach movements. Thus, to relieve morning sickness in pregnant women, ginger infusion can be consumed.

Improves Digestion If you're feeling bloated after eating a hearty burger or large portion of fries, a mixture of ginger, lemon and honey in hot water will help you get back into shape. Animal studies show that ginger can stimulate bile secretion and the activity of various digestive enzymes, leading to faster digestion of food.

In traditional medicine, ginger is often used for the intestines as a remedy for disorders. Its active substances accelerate the breakdown of gases and their elimination, helping well with bloating.

May Help in Weight Loss Ginger improves digestion and acts as a true fat burner, helping in regaining a healthy weight. One large scientific review published data from several dozen randomized controlled studies that proved that ginger can be used in the fight against extra pounds.

The effect of ginger for weight loss: accelerates metabolism, reduces appetite, normalizes blood sugar levels, increases “good” HDL cholesterol, stimulates the production of enzymes responsible for the breakdown of fat, increases body temperature, which allows you to burn more fat, prolongs the feeling of fullness.

Treats colds and sore throats In medicine, ginger is valued for its ability to prevent and treat colds. In Asia, it is used as an antibiotic to strengthen the immune system and calm infections. Having a warming, antipyretic and antiallergic effect, the root helps fight cold and flu symptoms. The antibacterial properties of the product kill pathogens in the throat and stimulate the body's defenses.

Relieves arthritis pain In Western countries, ginger is often used to reduce the inflammatory manifestations of rheumatism, arthritis and arthrosis, particularly as an essential oil applied directly to painful areas two to three times a day. A 2014 study shows that ginger acts as a natural analgesic, soothing pain in inflamed joints and also helping to increase joint mobility.

Heals and rejuvenates the skin. The antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal properties of ginger have determined its widespread use in cosmetics. In pharmacies you can find skin care products with its extract. Due to its antiseptic effect, the plant is an ingredient in creams for oily, combination, and rash- and acne-prone skin. It whitens, eliminates freckles and age spots. Rhizome extract is often included in products to strengthen and enhance hair growth and get rid of dandruff. In home care, ginger juice can be added as an additional component to shampoo, hair masks, or rubbed directly into the scalp.

Ginger “accelerates the blood”, helps improve metabolism in tissues and organs, therefore it is a component of many anti-cellulite creams and gels. Due to its antifungal properties, the extract is used in foot products and creams.

Ginger can be eaten in different ways: eaten raw, carefully peeled, mixed with other ingredients to make smoothies, herbal teas and energy drinks are prepared from it. Pickled ginger, candied in the form of candied fruits and powder for sprinkling dishes, is very popular. As a spice, it is often found in Asian sauces, spice mixtures, and lemonades. You can find ginger oil or root extract on sale. Ginger can also be purchased in tablets for oral administration.

Ginger water Infusion is one of the best ways to benefit from the health and digestive benefits of ginger. Ginger water improves digestion, cleanses the body of toxins, speeds up metabolism, and promotes weight loss.

Recipe: Pour one tablespoon of peeled and grated ginger root into a liter of warm water. Place in a dark place overnight to infuse. In the morning, add a teaspoon of honey and stir well. The resulting infusion should be drunk in small portions throughout the day. Course – 30 days.

You should not drink ginger water on an empty stomach or just before bed. Along with the drink, be sure to drink clean water. Keep it in moderation: no more than a liter of ginger water per day, as excessive consumption of this product can lead to heartburn and nausea.

Ginger tea

Tea with ginger and lemon Ingredients: - a piece of ginger - 3–4 cm long, - lemon -

- water - 500 ml, - honey - 1 tbsp. spoon

Preparation: Peel and grate the ginger, cut the lemon into thin slices. Pour boiling water over everything and leave to brew for 5–7 minutes. Tea with ginger and mint
Ingredients: - a piece of ginger - 5–6 cm long - lemon - ½ - water - 500 ml - mint - 1-2 sprigs - honey or sugar - to taste

Preparation: Cut the ginger and lemon into thin slices. Place in a saucepan and fill with water. Bring the liquid to a boil and reduce the heat. Add mint, boil the drink for another 10 minutes. Strain the tea and serve with your chosen sweetener. Tea with ginger and cinnamon
Ingredients: - a piece of ginger - 3-4 cm long - cinnamon - 1 stick - 700–750 ml of water - ground turmeric - 1 teaspoon - lemon juice - 60 ml - honey or sugar - to taste.

Preparation: Boil water in a saucepan. Add finely grated peeled ginger, cinnamon and turmeric. Brew the drink for about 5 minutes. Remove from heat and pour in lemon juice. Strain and serve tea with honey or sugar. The recommended average daily dosage of fresh root is 3-4 g (about 1 tsp). In powder you can take up to 500-1000 mg per day, in tincture before meals (10-20 drops), in infusion at the rate of 1 g of ginger per 150 ml of hot water 3 times a day. For external use, you can rub yourself with ginger essential oil or tincture of the root directly on the painful area, gargle with a solution of 1 tsp. ginger tincture diluted in warm water. The Chinese technique involves applying ginger poultices to painful joints.

Ginger can be used by almost everyone and in any form. However, precautions must be taken and therapeutic doses must be followed. If you overdose on ginger, you may experience some unwanted but not dangerous side effects, such as heartburn and stomach pain, gas and bloating, nausea, diarrhea, and heavier periods in women. Some people may also be allergic to ginger in the form of a skin rash.

Ginger is quite a spicy dish, so it is not recommended for gastritis, ulcers, heartburn, colitis, liver cirrhosis, pancreatic diseases, as well as severe hypertension. There is no need to eat on an empty stomach or in large quantities.

Ginger is contraindicated:

- ✗women in late pregnancy
- ✗nursing mothers
- ✗small children under three years old
- ✗people with diseases of the cardiovascular system and kidneys
- ✗for food allergies and individual intolerances.

Drug Interactions Various properties attributed to ginger (such as anticoagulant and hypoglycemic effects) suggest that its consumption may interfere with certain medications, herbs, or supplements. On this point, several authors recommend that people taking blood medications (such as heparin, Coumadin, or aspirin) or before surgery avoid consuming large amounts of ginger to reduce the risk of bleeding. Additionally, large doses of ginger may interfere with heart medications (cardiotonic effect) and diabetes medications (hypoglycemic effect). However, these interaction risks are theoretical and have not necessarily been observed in patients.

Unsafe during pregnancy Despite the fact that ginger can alleviate the condition of pregnant women by eliminating such unpleasant

pregnancy companions as nausea, heartburn, bloating, fatigue and irritability, in later stages it should be treated with great caution. Starting from the third trimester, the use of spice can be harmful due to its ability to thin the blood, which can lead to bleeding. On the eve of childbirth, ginger is strictly contraindicated.

May be an oral irritant. The active compounds in ginger that provide health benefits may cause irritation to the mucous membranes of the mouth and throat. This is especially true for people who are not accustomed to its specific burning taste. However, this most often occurs if you eat too much spice. If the recommended dosages are observed, ginger has a beneficial effect on the gums and teeth, as it effectively fights pathogenic microbes in the oral cavity.

For optimal preservation, it is best to keep ginger on a shelf in the refrigerator for 2-3 weeks. It can also be stored in a dry and ventilated place, like onions or potatoes. For long-term storage, you can keep it in the freezer and use it directly from frozen, grating it as needed. The pieces can be dried in the oven at low temperature with the door ajar for 10-12 hours, after boiling for 10 minutes to prevent sprouting during drying. If the root is peeled and cut into rings, there is no need to boil it; it will dry in a few days at room temperature. In Asia it is also preserved in sugar syrup. Maple syrup works well for this purpose. And another recipe for an original and infinitely long storage: put the rhizomes in a jar, pour sherry or cognac, close and put in the refrigerator.

References:

1. Olimjonovna, K. O. (2023). AYOLLARDA REPRODUKTIV TIZIM FAOLIYATINING O'ZGARISHIDA GIPOTERIOZ BILAN BIRGA KECHISHI. Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi, 10(3), 174-179.
2. Olimjonovna, K. O. (2024). HYPOTHYROIDISM AND REPRODUCTIVE DYSFUNCTION IN WOMEN. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 36(5), 75-82.
3. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 59-65.
4. Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 391-397.
5. Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences, 2(6), 5-11.
6. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture, 2(2), 22-26.
7. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 22, 199-205.
8. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. Gender issues, 7(6).
9. JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 18-22).
10. Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). Новый день в медицине, (4), 501-503.

11. Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. *Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА»*. Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.
12. Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. *Молодой ученый*, (26), 377-379.
13. Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 32-34.
14. Dzhalilova, Z. O., & Mirfajziev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 35-37.
15. Dzhalilova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 398-400.
16. Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 34-35.
17. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 190-198.
18. Dzhalilova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 400-402.
19. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(11), 29-34.
20. Джалилова, З. (2022). РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ МАКСИМ ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ДИАЛОГАХ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(21), 22-33.
21. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). A Speech Etiquette Formula for the Gender Communication Strategy. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 44-50.
22. Djalilova, Z. (2022). DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(12), 8-14.
23. Джалилова, З. О. (2022). НУТҚ ҲАРАКАТЛАРИДА ХУШМУОМАЛАЛИКНИНГ ГЕНДЕР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(5).
24. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(10), 14-21.
25. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(11), 15-20.
26. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 55-63.
27. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER-DETERMINED DIFFERENCES IN THE SPEECH OF LITERARY CHARACTERS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(12), 210-215.
28. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(13), 274-281.

29. Джалилова, З. (2022). ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ВЗГЛЯД НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya*, 1(7), 331-336.
30. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER XUSHMUOMALALIKKA ASOSLANGAN IBORALARNING SHAKLLANISHI. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(28), 303-308.
31. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & SHARIPOV, A. G. ALPHABET OF LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 338-339.
32. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & UBAJDULLOEV, A. U. U. COMPARISON DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 336-338.
33. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & JAKUBOV, U. S. NUMBERS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 339-341.
34. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. ADJECTIVE IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 332-334.
35. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. PRONOUNS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 334-336.
36. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, K. M. K. U. LATIN PRONOUNS. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 257-258.
37. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, M. K. U. VERBS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 255-257.
38. Djalilova, Z. O. (2023). A DISCOURSIIVE TURN IN THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC POLITENESS: TO THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC IMPOLITENESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 15-23.
39. Djalilova, Z. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY: ESSENCE, CHARACTERISTICS AND EFFICIENCY. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(23), 29-38.
40. Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POSITION OF TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(10), 31-42.
41. Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL CASE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(14), 9-15.
42. Джалилова, З. (2023). The notion of illocution in the theory of speech acts by John Austin. *Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке*, 1(1).
43. Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). ADAPTING TEACHING METHODS TO MODERN EDUCATIONAL TRENDS: PEDAGOGICAL ASPECT. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(10), 72-77.
44. Djalilova, Z. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND THEIR IMPLICATION FOR TEACHING ENGLISH. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11), 18-22.
45. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaimonovich, D. S. (2023). Influence of the Mode of Work and Recreation of the Student's Health. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 2(3), 3-5.
46. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.

47. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. *Достижения науки и образования*, (2 (82)), 120-126.
48. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 3(06), 53-64.
49. Jo'rayev, S., & Djalilova, Z. (2022). NEUROLOGICAL STATUS OF CHILDREN WITH INTRAUTERINE DEVELOPMENTAL DELAY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(9), 34-37.
50. Djalilova, Z. (2023). ADVANCING PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES: LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES TO ENHANCE THE INTEGRATION OF ENGLISH AND LATIN LANGUAGE INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(12), 54-60.
51. Djalilova, Z. (2023). ADVANCING CRITICAL THINKING PROFICIENCY THROUGH OPTIMIZED PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(12), 61-67.
52. Djalilova, Z. (2023). IMPROVING METHODOLOGIES FOR INTEGRATIVE ENGLISH AND LATIN LANGUAGE TEACHING USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(12 Part 2), 29-34.
53. Djalilova, Z. (2023). ELEVATING CRITICAL THINKING WITH EFFICIENT TEACHING METHODS (GEARED TOWARDS MEDICAL STUDENTS). *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 97-102.
54. Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). THE ART OF QUESTIONING: ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH EFFECTIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUES. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(11), 54-60.
55. Djalilova, Z. O., Tasheva, N. Z., Nematova, Z. T., & Nasrieva, G. Z. (2023). LEXICO-SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES IN MODERN ENGLISH (ANALYZING ITS BOTH LANGUAGE VARIANTS: BRITISH AND AMERICAN ENGLISH ONES). *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(S2), 4433-4445.